

Abstract: Country Report: Czech Republic

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The Czech Republic contains a number of extensive areas in which efforts are being made to preserve industrial heritage and put old industrial sites to new use. The biggest task, challenge and also problem in preserving industrial heritage in the Czech Republic is represented by the Ostrava industrial conurbation. The systematic documentation and evaluation of the conurbation's industrial heritage is carried out by the National Heritage Authority in order that the status of cultural heritage sites – and thus legal protection – is granted to the most important examples of the region's industrial heritage, not just those sites whose current owners agree with conservation efforts.

A key heritage site in the Ostrava conurbation is the complex of the Hlubina colliery, the coking plant and the Vítkovice blast furnace. A strategy has been drawn up for the conservation and rejuvenation of the site, based around a division of its various component parts into three categories, in order of importance: 1) the key parts of the technological process, for which conservation is recommended, 2) sites and technical facilities which cannot be put to new use, 3) those which can be put to new use. Currently, systematic renovation work is taking place on the site – which is divided between two owners – and studies have been drawn up detailing the future use of the site.

In view of the fact that the conservation and renewal of industrial heritage is an exceptionally complex, long-term and financially demanding issue, we recommend the establishment of an international group of experts on the relevant fields, under the auspices of ICOMOS and TICCIH, which will ensure greater stability of conceptions and project management.

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The Czech Republic contains a number of extensive areas in which efforts are being made to preserve industrial heritage and put old industrial sites to new use. These include, for example, the Kladno ironworks and coal mines, or the Karlín district of Prague, which is now (in 2007) undergoing wide-ranging reconstruction after damage by floods. The biggest task, challenge and also problem in preserving industrial heritage in the Czech Republic is represented by the Ostrava industrial conurbation. The major milestones in the development of the conurbation were the discovery of coal in the late 18th century, the foundation of the Vítkovice ironworks in 1828, the opening of the railway line from Bohumín to Vienna and its connection with the Wilhelm line to Berlin and then to Krakow – leading to the accelerated development of the conurbation up to the mid-20th century.

The late 1960s saw the demolition of the large complex of the Žofín ironworks in the city centre of Ostrava. This, together with the closure of several important coal mines, led to the first attempts to preserve the region's industrial heritage – not just in the form of museum pieces for exhibition and storage, but also as authentic sites and technical equipment preserved 'in situ'. These attempts by a number of enthusiasts from the artistic and intellectual community ultimately met with failure, nevertheless they gave rise to the first systematic documentation of the architectural and historic technical heritage of the Ostrava conurbation. Unfortunately, in the totalitarian conditions which followed the 1968 Warsaw Pact occupation of Czechoslovakia, it was not possible to continue the systematic documentation of industrial (at the time, known as 'strategic') production or to promote conservation activities. Exceptions to this rule were represented by the Anselm / Eduard Urx colliery and the Michal / Petr Cingr coal mine; in the

early 1980s, projects for the re-use of these sites were drawn up by students at the Architecture Faculty of the Technical University of Brno under the direction of Professor Zemánková. It was only after 1989, in the new political climate, that the Ostrava branch of the National Heritage Institute began to systematically document, compare and select sites and technical equipment for the purpose of conservation and legal protection.

The central motivation and philosophy behind the conservation of industrial heritage is to ensure that the status of cultural heritage sites – and thus legal protection – is granted to the most important examples of the region's industrial heritage, not just those sites whose current owners agree with conservation efforts. This principle has led to many conflicts, nevertheless, in our view, the aim of conserving the most important sites and equipment has been successfully achieved.

The **first step** towards this aim was to carry out a thorough documentation of all sites and technical equipment from individual industrial sectors (mining, metallurgy, rail transport, chemicals, energy, workers' housing).

The **second step** was to select the best-known representatives of milestones in the development of each sector (e.g. different types of pit-head winding gear towers), examples of the systemic mutual interconnections within the conurbation (interlinking of technological flows, the transport network, housing and the social environment), and the overall face of the urban landscape (with its panoramas and landmarks such as pit-heads and the blast furnaces); these criteria represent only the most important principles of selection and evaluation.

The **third step** was to set out the strategy for the choice of conservation method; this choice depends on the importance and degree of authenticity of the site or equipment. A range of options are open, from the 'last working day' principle (conservation after reconstruction) to 'mere' architectural restoration with the aim of restoring a site to its previous appearance, as with railway stations; these sites always continued to perform their original function, but were variously damaged over the years, subjected to unsuitable building work and alterations, and required the installation of new transport and operational technologies as well as other changes. The re-use of sites ('recycling') also presents a range of options, from their use as small-scale manufacturing and storage premises, to their use as museums containing authentic exhibitions of preserved technical equipment or didactic presentations, including gigantic items of technical equipment brought to the site from other locations.

It is our view that only by applying the full range of approaches with regard to the importance of specific sites and technical equipment is it possible to conserve the 'milestones' of our industrial cultural heritage and to revive the original atmosphere of the historical periods in which those milestones emerged.

A key industrial heritage site of the Ostrava conurbation – the Hlubina colliery, the coking plant, and the Vítkovice ironworks blast furnace

The Vítkovice ironworks were founded in 1828 in the vicinity of local coal deposits. In 1842 the Hlubina colliery was set up on the site, in order to bring the extraction of coal as close as possible to its main point of consumption. In this way, the technological flow – from coal extraction, through coke production, to the use of coke in iron production – was concentrated on the same site. This basic, 'textbook' technological interconnection of industrial production continued until the gradual winding down of extraction at Hlubina and iron production at the Vítkovice blast furnace in 1997.

After production was terminated, and following complex negotiations, the site was placed under legal protection, ranked alongside the most important heritage sites in the Czech Republic by being listed as a National Cultural Heritage Site. The Ministry of Culture and the Czech government took the decision to protect the entire locality on the basis of detailed

documentation, technical and architectural assessments, and calculations of the costs of 'stabilizing' and reviving the sites. The entire strategy was based around the differentiation of individual parts of the site and equipment according to their importance, with the aim of identifying the real costs of their renewal:

The **key parts of the technological process** (the pit-head building, winding gear, processing plant, coking plant, blast furnace and other auxiliary technical facilities) were earmarked as a future tour circuit for visitors, with the aim of fully preserving the authenticity of the environment, including the outward appearance of the equipment and sites.

The **sites and technical facilities which cannot be put to new use** but which contribute to the environment and act as urban landmarks. These parts of the site were originally termed 'controlled ruins', but this name was soon dropped because it proved unacceptable to political representatives, who were reluctant to support the existence of a 'ruin' in their city centre. There was also a change of opinion to accept the necessity of carrying out basic work to reduce safety risks, by taking down some suspended structures and stabilizing construction systems (statics, re-roofing); the site is constantly monitored, and necessary repairs can be carried out as needed.

The **sites which can be put to new use** include former bathrooms converted into administrative premises or exhibition halls, or a gas-holder used as a multipurpose hall. The new uses were initially set out only in approximate terms, but the plans have gradually become more specific as ownership structures have been stabilized and new owners have expressed their own visions.

Currently, the site is divided between two owners. The part containing the Hlubina colliery – owned by DIAMO, the state-owned successor to the former mining company – is undergoing systematic renovation work, and negotiations have begun on transferring this part of the site to the National Heritage Authority. For the part containing the coking plant and blast furnace of the Vítkovice ironworks – which has been in private ownership since 2003 – studies detailing possibilities for future use have been drawn up on the initiative of the current owner.

Conclusion

Due to their outstanding importance, four industrial sites in Ostrava (Hlubina colliery, coking plant and Vítkovice blast furnace; Anselm / Eduard Urš colliery; Michal / Petr Cingr colliery; Vrbovice ventilation shaft) have been selected by the National Heritage Authority to be submitted for UNESCO listing.

The preservation, rejuvenation and new use of technical heritage sites is a complex matter, involving a combination of various interests as well as various expert approaches. For this reason, the rejuvenation of large-scale industrial heritage sites or systems is always a result of long-term conceptions involving a demanding search for complex, often painful compromises.

In view of the fact that long-term and financially demanding projects are impacted on by a wide range of changes and decisions, we recommend the establishment of an international group of experts on the relevant fields, under the auspices of ICOMOS and TICCIH, which will act as an undisputed expert authority able to assess the importance and uniqueness of specific locations, or to adjudicate on key rejuvenation projects. In this way, the group will contribute to a higher level of professional quality and greater stability in the protection and conservation of industrial heritage.